

Project CHANGES- Spoke 4

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Author(s)	Cavallo Perin, Roberto (https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3217-6591): Dipartimento di Giurisprudenza, Università degli Studi di Torino Gualandi, Bianca (https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8202-8493): ARIC - Area Ricerca, Università di Bologna Paruzzo, Francesca (https://orcid.org/0009-0003-9488-4555): Dipartimento di Giurisprudenza, Università degli Studi di Torino Peroni, Silvio (https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0530-4305): Dipartimento di Filologia Classica e Italianistica, Università di Bologna
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Spoke information

Scientific coordinator

Silvio Peroni – silvio.peroni@unibo.it – <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0530-4305>

Dipartimento di Filologia Classica e Italianistica

Alma Mater Studiorum – Università di Bologna

Via Zamboni 32, 40126 Bologna (BO), Italia

Scientific co-coordinator

Gianluca Genovese – gianluca.genovese@unisob.na.it – <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1064-2061>

Dipartimento di Scienze Umanistiche

Università degli Studi Suor Orsola Benincasa

Via Suor Orsola 10, 80135 Napoli (NA), Italia

Spoke partners

No	Name	Acronym	Role
1	Alma Mater Studiorum – Università di Bologna	UNIBO	Spoke leader
2	Università degli Studi Suor Orsola Benincasa	UNISOB	Spoke co-leader
3	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche	CRN	Member
4	DTC Lazio	DTC	Member
5	Engineering	ENG	Member
6	Università degli Studi di Bari Aldo Moro	UNIBA	Member
7	Università degli Studi di Ferrara	UNIFE	Affiliated by "convenzione"
8	Università degli Studi di Firenze	UNIFI	Member
9	Università degli Studi di Parma	UNIPR	Affiliated by "convenzione"
10	Università degli Studi di Torino	UNITO	Member

Executive Summary

The activities of Spoke 4 - *Virtual Technologies for museums and art collections* focus on the impact of digital cultural heritage (DHC), compared to the current views on tangible and intangible heritage. The final objective is to make the digital enhancement of cultural heritage a permanent and widespread practice in museums and art collections, in order to:

- Increase the knowledge and organization of artifacts in all forms
- Expand the general public involvement
- Improve and make more sustainable the exhibition potential
- Improve accessibility, inclusiveness, participation, enjoyment and sustainability.

In addition, in line with the objectives of the NRRP¹, the project reinforces multidisciplinary research on a topic of strategic value; introduces innovative models for basic research, promoting synergies between universities, cultural heritage institutions and companies (through the implementation of pilot studies involving national museums and art collections); empowers existing research infrastructures and supports innovation by developing specific competences.

This Data Management Plan describes the categories of data produced and re-used within the project and details how they are handled in a transparent manner and according to FAIR principles and open science principles.

This deliverable is a living document and has evolved during the lifespan of the project. The first version was published in May 2023; the second version in February 2024; this final planned update has been published in February 2025 (M27 of the project).

¹ National Recovery and Resilience Plan, <https://www.italiadomani.gov.it/content/sogei-ng/it/en/home.html>

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1. Introduction

The participants to Spoke 4 – *Virtual Technologies for museums and art collections* met online (via Microsoft Teams) on 21 April 2023 to discuss Research Data Management (RDM) in the context of the Spoke's activities. The consortium discussed how to implement an efficient RDM strategy in line with FAIR principle and open science practices. After a brief introduction on FAIR RDM tools and practices in the context of Digital Cultural Heritage (DCH), the structure and purpose of this Data Management Plan (DMP) was discussed. The group agreed on a common strategy to draft and revise this document and published its first version on Zenodo² in May 2023 (M6).

The DMP was then updated between January and February 2024. New datasets were added to Annex I and the body of the document was edited collaboratively. This second version was published on Zenodo in February 2024 (M15).

The current document is the product of a third round of revisions by all partners, taking place between December 2024 and February 2025. New datasets have again been added to Annex I, some have been replaced, and the body of the document has been modified significantly, especially in [section 3.4](#), by adding 5 new sections on the Italian and European regulatory framework governing the digitization and reuse of cultural heritage, with a focus on licensing, faithful and creative reproductions, and the implications of the Cultural Heritage Code. The role of the Creative Commons Zero (CC0) license in this context and its limitations concerning current regulations are now also discussed.

This third and final planned version has been published on Zenodo in February 2025 (M27).

² <https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4>

2. Data Summary

For a brief description of the project, please see the [Executive Summary](#), above.

Table 1 below provides and overviews the **categories of data** that the project generates and re-uses; examples are provided, as well as the **file formats** the data will be stored and disseminated in.

For a detailed list of the dataset that the Spoke partners are producing and re-using in the context of the project, please see [Annex I](#).

Table 1: Overview of the types and formats of data that the project generates and/or re-uses

Types of data	Examples	Formats
3D models	e.g., 3D models containing geometry, material and texture information	glTF, GLB, obj, mtl, png, tiff, jpg, e57, ply, fbx, x3d, collada
Images	e.g., digital reproductions of manuscripts, digital reproductions of artworks, acquired and processed photos, panoramas	tiff, png, jpg, raw
Tabular	e.g., tourist flows related to cultural places, questionnaire answers	csv, tsv, xlsx, ods, accdb
Textual (including documents that are mostly but not exclusively textual)	e.g., excerpts from literary texts, semi-structured interviews, newly produced texts like papers and dissemination material, logs of user behaviour, web pages and stylesheets	pdf, docx, pptx, txt, md, xhtml, css, scss
Audio	e.g., interviews, music, interactive guides	mp3, wav
Video	e.g., original content for storytelling experience	mp4, mov, mkv, MOD
Software	e.g., research software, scripts, configuration files	py, js, yaml, ini, toml
Other	e.g., metadata, cross media books, tactile reproductions	RDF formats (e.g., ttl, nt, nq, json, jsonld), stl; 3MF, exr, insp, dng, ARM, ingp

Considering the potentially high number of high-resolution images, 3D models and videos, the **size of several datasets is in the terabyte range**. Each partner has saved their own data on their own institutional/corporate storage space (see [Section 5](#), Table 3, below).

3. FAIR data

3.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

According to FAIR principles³, all data produced during the project has **associated metadata and persistent unique identifiers (PIDs)**⁴ assigned as early as possible. If existing data and metadata (e.g., from museums and galleries) have already been assigned a PID, this is always used to refer and point to the data.

Decisions on **metadata standards** have taken into accounts schemas adopted by museums and galleries and, in any case, follow existing standards widely used in the cultural heritage sector. At a minimum, the findability of each dataset is insured through the provision of general-purpose metadata (e.g., Dublin Core, DataCite) via the repositories chosen for long term preservation. In many cases however, widely used metadata models like CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CIDOC CRM)⁵ and its extensions, such as CRM Digital (CRMdig)⁶ and FRBRoo⁷, have been further employed to express data semantics for digital cultural heritage. CIDOC CRM provides semantic constructs for documenting cultural heritage in the broadest sense. CRMdig extends CIDOC CRM to specifically address the needs of digital cultural heritage, incorporating concepts like digital objects, acquisition and software activities. FRBRoo allows for the representation of cultural heritage objects in terms of the abstractions expressed in the Functional Requirements for Bibliographic Records (FRBR) conceptual model⁸.

³ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

⁴ Such as DOIs (for most digital objects), and Software Heritage ID (for software)

⁵ <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/>

⁶ <http://www.ics.forth.gr/isl/CRMdig/>

⁷ <http://iflstandards.info/ns/fr/frbr/frbroo/>

⁸ FRBR represents bibliographic entities by splitting them into four conceptual objects: Works, Expressions, Manifestations, and Items. Works represent abstract intellectual creations, while Expressions denote specific

During data collection and analysis, each partner has undertaken to host their data on **GDPR-compliant cloud services** that provide **automatic versioning**. Software has been developed on discipline-specific platforms that also provide built-in versioning (e.g., git). For other types of data, clear version numbers have been provided within the file names, e.g. in the form:

```
filename_with_underscores_DDMMYYYY.extension
```

as indicated in the Spoke coordination guide. This has ensured transparent research management, has helped collaboration, and has minimised the risks of losing or overwriting files and data throughout.

3.2. Making data accessible

The table below outlines which data repositories have been selected to ensure continued accessibility to the datasets (see also [Annex I](#)). **Most datasets are openly available**, while others are shared with some restrictions (see also the section [Increase data re-use](#) below).

Table 2: List of datasets, relative repository for long-term preservation and access license

N	Summary description of content	Repository	License	Reasons for controlling access
1	3D models of curved surfaces	Zenodo	CC BY-SA 4.0	Ethical reasons may limit reuse
2	3D models of small objects	Zenodo	CC BY-SA 4.0	Ethical reasons may limit reuse
3	3D and 2D models	Zenodo	CC BY-SA 4.0	Ethical reasons may limit reuse
4	3D mesh models	Zenodo	CC BY-NC-ND 4.0	Reggia di Caserta MIC policy
5	Documents printed or on-line	Zenodo	CC 0	
6	Documents printed or on-line	Zenodo	CC 0	

realizations of works. Manifestations embody expressions in physical form, and Items are individual exemplars of manifestations accessible to users. For more information on FRBR, please refer to Tillett, B. (2005). What is FRBR? A conceptual model for the bibliographic universe. *The Australian Library Journal*, 54(1), 24-30. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00049670.2005.10721710>.

7	Questionnaires	Zenodo	not accessible (controlled/closed access)	The data contained in the questionnaires will remain for the exclusive use of the research team
8	Texts (brochure, articles, catalogues, general documents)	Zenodo	CC BY 4.0	
9	Audio (podcast, interview, music, interactive guide)	Zenodo	CC BY 4.0	
10	3D models and photogrammetric images	Zenodo	CC BY 4.0	
11	Images, Gigapixel images	Zenodo	CC BY 4.0	
12	Video	Zenodo	CC BY 4.0	
13	Metadata	Zenodo	CC 0	
14	Raster Images, 3D models, data specification for transmission of 3D scenes and models	Zenodo	CC 0, when possible	Some models may require a different license depending on the restrictions of the cultural heritage institutions or the person owning the original object
15	Raster Images, 3D models, data specification for transmission of 3D scenes and models	Zenodo	CC 0, when possible	Some models may require a different license depending on the restrictions of the cultural heritage institutions or the person owning the original object
16	Raster Images, Digital reproduction of archive materials, 3D Models, photogrammetric images of artifacts, findings and structures	Zenodo	to be decided	Requirements of the rights holder
17	3D and 2D models, audiovisual content, text	tbd	CC BY 4.0	
18	Text (LLM benchmarking)	Zenodo	CC BY 4.0	
19	RDF and OWL documents, text (narrative patterns and vocabularies)	Zenodo	CC BY 4.0	
20	Text (anonymized logs of user behavior)	Zenodo	CC BY-NC 4.0	Submitted to ethical considerations about the user- contributed origin of data
21	Raw metadata of museum collections	Zenodo	CC 0	

22	Narrative contents for digital storytelling	Zenodo	CC 0	
23	Texts related to manuscript collection	Zenodo	CC BY 4.0	
24	Presentations for dissemination purposes	Zenodo	CC BY 4.0	
25	Images and 3D models	Zenodo	CC BY-NC-ND 4.0	UNISOB policy
26	UX assessment data	Zenodo	CC BY 4.0	
27	UX assessment data	Zenodo	CC BY 4.0	
28	Texts (digital storytelling; interview transcripts and more)	Zenodo	CC BY 4.0	
29	Texts (brochure; articles; catalogues and more)	Zenodo	CC BY 4.0	
30	Video interviews	Zenodo	CC BY 4.0	
31	Texts (brochure; articles; catalogues and more)	Zenodo	CC BY 4.0	
32	Dataset of the Gattelli Literary Park	Zenodo	CC 0, CC BY-SA 4.0, when possible	More restrictive licenses may be necessary to protect the privacy of people participating in interviews or in the case of different needs of any surviving heirs of the author
33	MELODY	Zenodo	ISC	
34	MELODY API	Zenodo	ISC	
35	Acquisition and objects (ods and csv tables)	Zenodo	CC BY 0	
36	Metadata Conversion Plugin	Zenodo/Software Heritage	Apache	
37	Dataset SMA Museo Leonardi	Zenodo	CC BY-NC-ND 4.0	In discussion with owner institutions
38	Dataset of the Aliano Literary Park	Zenodo	CC 0, CC BY-SA 4.0, when possible	More restrictive licenses may be necessary to protect the privacy of people participating in interviews or in the case of different needs of any surviving heirs of the author

Almost all partners have opted for depositing data in **Zenodo**⁹, a generalist repository that guarantees long term preservation, attributes DOIs to all archived datasets and all versions, supports open licenses and different access levels and complies with OpenAIRE

⁹ <https://zenodo.org/>

requirements for data archives. Zenodo also allows users to create specific pages dedicated to a specific project or community; the page dedicated to the Spoke is available at: <https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/>

It is important to note that there has been no preclusion, from the coordinating partner, on using other data repositories alongside or in place of Zenodo.

3.3. Making data interoperable

The interoperability of project data and technologies – their “ability to work together with other systems”¹⁰ – has been pursued on all levels. Indeed, creating scalable solutions, deployable across cultural institutions, and promoting the creation of “an ecosystem of services” for Cultural Heritage is one of the main objectives of the project:

1. **Standard formats have been used for all generated data** (see [Table 1](#)) as not to be bound to any proprietary software applications. When specific pay-for software has been used during data collection and analysis (e.g., MS Word, Excel), files have been exported to open formats whenever possible (e.g., .txt, .rtf, .pdf) to **facilitate exchange and re-use** and **guarantee long-term preservation**. Regarding 3D formats, the adoption of glTF, an interoperable open standard¹¹ targeting interactive Web3D applications, has been highly recommended. This standard guarantees high interoperability with existing 3D platforms/services, re-use and integration of licensing information inside the format.
2. CH data has been collected, analysed and otherwise treated **following existing guidelines** as much as possible, such as those published by the Italian Ministry of Culture in the context of the *Piano nazionale di digitalizzazione del patrimonio culturale*

¹⁰ <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/interoperability>

¹¹ Now ISO standard - <https://www.iso.org/standard/83990.html>

(PND)¹², and the *Cultural Heritage Data Reuse Charter*¹³. The research data management practices described in this DMP are also fully compliant with those included in the DMP of the CHANGES project (Hub).

3. Commonly used **controlled vocabularies and ontologies** (e.g., CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model¹⁴) have been adopted whenever possible; otherwise, an explanation has been provided together with rich documentation. If ontologies or controlled vocabularies have been produced as part of the project, they are described in this DMP or elsewhere to facilitate their reuse.¹⁵
4. The **methodologies and workflows** used for data collection and analysis, including to produce FAIR-compliant data, are **thoroughly documented**. Equally, software and data deposited in a repository are accompanied by relevant documentation – i.e., all information necessary to evaluate, understand and reuse it – in the form of a README file or similar.

3.4. Increase data re-use (R. Cavallo Perin; F. Paruzzo)

Please see [Table 2](#) for a list of the datasets and relative access license.

3.4.1 Premises

The digitization of cultural heritage represents both a challenge and an opportunity for the conservation, enhancement, and accessibility of cultural assets. The sections that follow

¹² <https://digitalibrary.cultura.gov.it/il-piano/>; <https://docs.italia.it/italia/icdp/>

¹³ <https://datacharter.hypotheses.org/77>

¹⁴ "The CIDOC CRM represents an 'ontology' for cultural heritage information i.e. it describes in a formal language the explicit and implicit concepts and relations relevant to the documentation of cultural heritage. The primary role of the CIDOC CRM is to serve as a basis for mediation of cultural heritage information and thereby provide the semantic 'glue' needed to transform today's disparate, localised information sources into a coherent and valuable global resource". See <https://www.cidoc-crm.org/node/202>

¹⁵ Cfr. PND: <https://docs.italia.it/italia/icdp/icdp-pnd-dmp-docs/it/v1.0-giugno-2022/scheda-progetto/open-data.html#ontologie-e-vocabolari-di-riferimento-i-c>

(3.4.2 to 3.4.5) outline the Italian and European regulatory framework governing the digitization and reuse of cultural heritage, with a focus on licensing, faithful and creative reproductions, and the implications of the Cultural Heritage Code. The role of the Creative Commons Zero (CC0) license in this context and its limitations concerning current regulations will also be discussed.

3.4.2 Regulatory framework for the Digitization of Cultural Heritage

Italian and European regulations have evolved to regulate digitization activities and the reuse of digital cultural assets. The main legal references include:

a. Italian Constitution

Article 9: The Republic promotes the development of culture and scientific and technical research. It protects the landscape and the historical and artistic heritage of the Nation.

Article 33: Art and science are free, and teaching is free as well.

Article 117: Distributes legislative competencies between the State and Regions, with the protection of cultural heritage falling under the exclusive jurisdiction of the State.

b. Cultural Heritage and Landscape Code (Legislative Decree 42/2004)

Article 107: Regulates the conditions for reproducing cultural heritage, requiring prior authorization and setting possible limitations.

Article 108: Governs the commercial use of cultural heritage reproductions, subjecting them to the payment of fees and specific authorizations.

Article 109: Allows managing entities to adopt regulations to establish reproduction methods and tariffs.

c. European Directive 2019/1024 (PSI) and Legislative Decree 200/2021

Includes cultural data held by museums, archives, and libraries, encouraging public reuse while allowing exceptions for the protection of cultural heritage.

d. European Directive 2019/790 (Copyright) and Legislative Decree 177/2021

Establishes that faithful reproductions of public domain works cannot be subject to new copyright. Introduces exceptions for digitization by cultural institutions for conservation and research purposes.

e. National Digitization Plan (PND) 2022-2026

Provides operational guidelines for the digitization and enhancement of digital cultural heritage.

3.4.3 Faithful and creative reproductions: authorization and licensing

Digital reproductions of cultural heritage can be classified into two main categories:

- a. Faithful reproductions: Exact copies without artistic originality (e.g., scans, technical photographs).
 - Authorization: Require authorization from the owning entity under Article 107, except for specific exemptions.
 - Commercial use: Requires further authorization and payment of fees.
 - Licenses (CC0/CC BY): Not applicable, as they do not generate new copyright.
- b. Creative reproductions: Artistic interpretations or digital reworkings (e.g., 3D models, artistic photographs).
 - Authorization: Even if the digital work is new, it remains subject to the authorization of the original entity.
 - Commercial use: In addition to the author's rights, compliance with restrictions on the original cultural asset is required.
 - Licenses (CC0/CC BY): Possible, but do not eliminate the obligation of authorization for reuse.

3.4.4 The role of the CC0 License and its legal limitations

The Creative Commons Zero (CC0) license allows the author to waive property rights and release the work into the public domain. However, for the digitization of public cultural assets, there are certain restrictions:

- For faithful reproductions: CC0 is not applicable, as copyright does not apply to exact copies of public domain works. Their use remains regulated by Article 107 of the Cultural Heritage Code.
- For creative reproductions: The author may release their work under CC0, but the user must still obtain authorization from the cultural entity for certain uses, particularly commercial ones. Persistence of moral rights: In Italy, moral rights are inalienable, so even with CC0, the original author retains the right to attribution and the integrity of the work. Similarly, the CC BY license, which allows reuse with attribution, does not remove the obligation for authorization when using images or models derived from cultural heritage.

3.4.5 Conclusions and perspectives

The current regulatory framework imposes significant limitations on the use of open licenses such as CC0 for digital works based on cultural heritage. The main issues include:

- a. The need for prior authorization even for advanced scientific reproductions.
- b. The requirement for fees for commercial uses.
- c. The fact that CC0 and CC BY do not eliminate the restrictions imposed by the Cultural Heritage Code.

To overcome these obstacles, it may be useful to develop flexible licensing models, which integrate Italian regulatory constraints with open access needs. Greater cooperation between public and private entities could also facilitate a balance between protection and the promotion of digital cultural heritage.

5. Allocation of resources

Data collection and analysis are integral to the Spoke activities and are covered by the effort of the people involved in the project.

Partners have not reported specific expenses for data management, e.g., for extra storage space, or for the purchase of specific tools. Long-term preservation in Zenodo comes free of charge for datasets smaller than 50GB.

6. Data security

Partners have undertaken to store their data on GDPR-compliant cloud services. If personal data have been collected, they are further protected (e.g., via file encryption) and never shared.

Research data stored in computers, laptops, intranets or hard drives are accessible only after logging in with username and password (periodically modified according to national law provisions for data security) and are protected by updated antiviruses.

Backup copies (ideally 2) of data and other files are routinely made and saved on different supports.

Table 3: Type of storage and backup policies of partner institutions

Partner	Type of storage	Backup policies
Alma Mater Studiorum – Università di Bologna	MS OneDrive, Uni laptops	All the data produced will be backed up on a new University server specifically made available for this purpose
Università degli Studi Suor Orsola Benincasa	Google Drive, Uni laptops	Google Drive restoring of deleted files
Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche	Sharepoint Unibo, Nextcloud, PC CNR	Nextcloud versioning, External hard disks, OneDrive recovery
DTC Lazio	Google Drive, laptops owned by DTC LAZIO	Google Drive, laptops owned by DTC LAZIO
Engineering	Sharepoint/One drive, Laptop	OneDrive file recovery functions

Università degli Studi di Bari Aldo Moro	Uni laptops, external hard disks, izi.TRAVEL	External hard disks, izi.TRAVEL (License Terms: http://izi.travel/legal/privacy-statement)
Università degli Studi di Firenze	Google Drive	Google Drive, NAS (locally placed at University of Florence)
Università degli Studi di Torino	Google Drive, laptops owned by the University	Google Drive, laptops owned by the University

7. Ethics

Some project activities revolve around administering surveys/questionnaires to groups of people. **Informed consent forms** for participation in research and for sharing data are included in each data collection task dealing with personal data and the information included in the forms is accepted by each participant before data collection. Acceptance is pursued by means of signature of participants or legal guardians, or by means of clicking on the relevant boxes for accepting terms and conditions of use.

As mentioned, all partners undertake to store their data on GDPR-compliant cloud services and to **protect any personal data further**, for example via encryption, never sharing them with anybody. Storage devices, such as laptops and memory sticks, are appropriately protected from unauthorized access and stored securely.

When possible and appropriate, research data have been **anonymized** (e.g., cleaned of all personal data) and shared with the consortium or the wider public.

The activities of the Spoke involve complex intellectual property considerations. Each project partner is responsible for:

- **clearing all existing intellectual property rights** (e.g., when reproducing a copyrighted work of art, or reusing data from other projects), with the help of legal experts, if necessary;
- make an informed decision, at the time of deposit at the latest, on the **type of reuse license to attach to the data they produce**.

Please refer to [section 3.4](#) for an outline of the Italian and European regulatory framework governing the digitization and reuse of cultural heritage, with a focus on licensing, faithful and creative reproductions, and the implications of the Cultural Heritage Code

Acknowledgements

We wish to thank all participants to WP1 for their collaboration in defining a research data management workflow for the project and in drafting this document. We are also extremely grateful to our external reviewers, Tiziana Mancinelli e Mario Marino, who read the first version of this document and provided precious feedback.

Annex I: Datasets

Thanks to the partners' input, we have carried out a **census of the datasets created or re-used** in the context of the Spoke.

Dataset number	1
WP number	WP4
Creator	Montaldo, Silvano (0000-0003-0820-8730)
Other contributor/s	Amitrano, Cristina; Damiano, Rossana; Mensa, Enrico
Rights holder/s	University of Turin
Dataset title	CHANGES - SPOKE 4, WP4, SMA01
The data set is	new
Status	not yet available
Data types	3D Models of curved surfaces (scanned tattoos)
Data formats	glTF, GLB, jpeg; other suitable formats will be taken into account at a later stage of the research
Dataset size	400G
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC BY-SA 4.0, "Attribution-ShareAlike", https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/
Reasons for limiting access	Ethical reasons may limit reuse
Related output	Lombroso Museum Catalogue

Dataset number	2
WP number	WP4
Creator	Pennacini, Cecilia (0000-0003-4626-4290)
Other contributor/s	Amitrano, Cristina; Damiano, Rossana; Mensa, Enrico
Rights holder/s	University of Turin
Dataset title	CHANGES - SPOKE 4, WP4 SMA02
The data set is	re-used
Status	in progress
Data types	3D models of small objects (3D models, laser scans and tomographies)
Data formats	glTF, GLB, jpeg; other suitable formats will be taken into account at a later stage of the research
Dataset size	100G
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC BY-SA 4.0, "Attribution-ShareAlike", https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/
Reasons for limiting access	Ethical reasons may limit reuse
Related output	

Dataset number	3
WP number	WP4
Creator	Montaldo, Silvano (0000-0003-0820-8730)
Other contributor/s	Amitrano, Cristina; Damiano, Rossana; Mensa, Enrico
Rights holder/s	University of Turin
Dataset title	CHANGES - SPOKE 4, WP4 SMA03
The data set is	new
Status	not yet available
Data types	3D and 2D Models (informal art objects; drawing, paintings, other artefacts)
Data formats	glTF, GLB, jpeg, tiff; other suitable formats will be taken into account at a later stage of the research
Dataset size	400g
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC BY-SA 4.0, "Attribution-ShareAlike", https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/
Reasons for limiting access	Ethical reasons may limit reuse
Related output	Lombroso Museum Catalogue

Dataset number	4
WP number	WP4
Creator	Genovese, Gianluca (0000-0002-1064-2061)
Other contributor/s	Maffei, Tiziana; Montanari, Roberto

Rights holder/s	Reggia di Caserta
Dataset title	Digital Objects from project Reggia di Caserta – RC3DT (CHANGES – SPOKE 4)
The data set is	new
Status	in progress
Data types	Digital objects included in the AR storytelling application of the Queen apartments of the Royal Palace of Caserta in the form of 3D mesh models.
Data formats	.GLTF/.GLB
Dataset size	The calculation of the Dataset size is in progress.
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC BY-NC-ND 4.0, "Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivatives", https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-nd/4.0/
Reasons for limiting access	Reggia di Caserta MIC policy
Related output	3D mesh models of the artworks used in the AR app.

Dataset number	5
WP number	WP4
Creator	Benvenuti, Giuliana (0000-0001-8469-2814)
Other contributor/s	Bagnaresi, Davide; Battilani, Patrizia; Boschi, Federica; Cattani, Maurizio; Gasperina Geroni, Riccardo; Iannucci, Alessandro; Giacomini, Federica; Obbiso, Sara; Mantellini, Simone; Pasini, Roberto; Putzolu, Cristiano; Santopuoli, Nicola; Stracuzzi, Riccardo; Turci, Monica; Montanari, Roberto; Villani, Paola; Albano, Ezia; Baldassarre, Michele; Bonacini, Elisa; Corriero, Michele; De Luca, Ylenia; Leonardi, Andrea; Mancini, Maria Giovanna; Massaro, Stefania; Perla, Loredana; Santacroce, Maria Teresa; Savino, Daniela; Mariniello, Nicola
Rights holder/s	Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna Università degli Studi Suor Orsola Benincasa – Napoli Università degli studi di Bari Aldo Moro Engineering Ingegneria Informatica SPA, Napoli
Dataset title	CHANGES - SPOKE 4, WP4, Publication of papers on literary parks
The data set is	new
Status	not yet available
Data types	Documents printed or on-line
Data formats	MS Word format, exported to open standard format for preservation (e.g.,.txt, .pdf), Web
Dataset size	20 GB
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC 0, "No Rights Reserved", https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/public-domain/cc0/

Reasons for limiting access	
Related output	All other datasets will be used for these publications.

Dataset number	6
WP number	WP4
Creator	Benvenuti, Giuliana (0000-0001-8469-2814)
Other contributor/s	Bagnaresi, Davide; Battilani, Patrizia; Boschi, Federica; Cattani, Maurizio; Cornaglia, Marco; Gasperina Geroni, Riccardo; Iannucci, Alessandro; Mantellini, Simone; Pasini, Roberto; Putzolu, Cristiano; Santopuoli, Nicola; Stracuzzi, Riccardo; Turci, Monica; Montanari, Roberto; Villani, Paola; Albano, Ezia; Baldassarre, Michele; Bonacini, Elisa; Corriero, Michele; De Luca, Ylenia; Leonardi, Andrea; Mancini, Maria Giovanna; Massaro, Stefania; Perla, Loredana; Santacroce, Maria Teresa; Savino, Daniela; Team Engineering
Rights holder/s	Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna Università degli Studi Suor Orsola Benincasa – Napoli Università degli studi di Bari Aldo Moro Engineering Ingegneria Informatica SPA, Napoli
Dataset title	CHANGES - SPOKE 4, WP 4, Flyers and brochures for dissemination events
The data set is	new
Status	not yet available
Data types	Documents printed or on-line
Data formats	MS Word format, exported to open standard format for preservation (e.g., .txt, .pdf), Web
Dataset size	10 GB
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC 0, "No Rights Reserved", https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/public-domain/cc0/
Reasons for limiting access	
Related output	All other datasets will be used for these flyers and brochures.

Dataset number	7
WP number	WP4
Creator	Corriero, Michele (0000-0002-7310-4324)
Other contributor/s	Bonacini, Elisa
Rights holder/s	Università degli Studi di Bari Aldo Moro
Dataset title	CHANGES - SPOKE 4, WP 4, Questionnaires for school stakeholders regarding the Carlo Levi and Grazia Deledda literary parks
The data set is	new
Status	not yet available

Data types	Textual, tabular
Data formats	MS Word and Excel formats, exported to open standard format for preservation (e.g., .txt, .pdf, or similar), Excel format, exported to open standard format for preservation (e.g., .csv)
Dataset size	5 GB
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	not accessible (controlled/closed access)
Reasons for limiting access	The data contained in the questionnaires will remain for the exclusive use of the research team.
Related output	

Dataset number	8
WP number	WP4
Creator	Thun Hohenstein, Ursula (0000-0003-2835-3679)
Other contributor/s	Parisi, Chiara (0009-0005-6887-2467)
Rights holder/s	Sistema Museale di Ateneo - Università di Ferrara, Italia
Dataset title	CHANGES - SPOKE 4, WP1, SMA_ML_TEXT, v001
The data set is	re-used; new
Status	in progress
Data types	Forms, brochure, articles, catalogues, educational book, monographs, general documents
Data formats	PDF
Dataset size	5 terabyte
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC BY 4.0, "Attribution", https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
Reasons for limiting access	
Related output	

Dataset number	9
WP number	WP4
Creator	Thun Hohenstein, Ursula (0000-0003-2835-3679)
Other contributor/s	Parisi, Chiara (0009-0005-6887-2467)
Rights holder/s	Sistema Museale di Ateneo - University of Ferrara, Italy
Dataset title	CHANGES - SPOKE 4, WP1, SMA_ML_AUDIO, v001
The data set is	re-used; new
Status	not yet available
Data types	Podcast, interview, music, interactive guide
Data formats	mp3
Dataset size	1 terabyte
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC BY 4.0, "Attribution", https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/

Reasons for limiting access	
Related output	

Dataset number	10
WP number	WP4
Creator	Thun Hohenstein, Ursula (0000-0003-2835-3679)
Other contributor/s	Parisi, Chiara (0009-0005-6887-2467)
Rights holder/s	Sistema Museale di Ateneo - University of Ferrara, Italia
Dataset title	CHANGES - SPOKE 4, WP1, SMA_ML_3D, v001
The data set is	re-used; new
Status	in progress
Data types	3D projects, 3D models, photogrammetric images
Data formats	obj, pdf, jpeg
Dataset size	12 terabyte
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC BY 4.0, "Attribution", https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
Reasons for limiting access	
Related output	

Dataset number	11
WP number	WP4
Creator	Thun Hohenstein, Ursula (0000-0003-2835-3679)
Other contributor/s	Parisi, Chiara (0009-0005-6887-2467)
Rights holder/s	Sistema Museale di Ateneo - University of Ferrara, Italia
Dataset title	CHANGES - SPOKE 4, WP1, SMA_ML_IMAGES, v001
The data set is	re-used; new
Status	in progress
Data types	Images, Gigapixel images
Data formats	jpeg, tiff, png
Dataset size	7 terabyte
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC BY 4.0, "Attribution", https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
Reasons for limiting access	
Related output	

Dataset number	12
WP number	WP4
Creator	Thun Hohenstein, Ursula (0000-0003-2835-3679)
Other contributor/s	Parisi, Chiara (0009-0005-6887-2467)
Rights holder/s	Sistema Museale di Ateneo - University of Ferrara, Italia
Dataset title	CHANGES - SPOKE 4, WP1, SMA_ML_VIDEO,v001
The data set is	re-used; new
Status	in progress
Data types	Video
Data formats	mp4, mov
Dataset size	5 terabyte
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC BY 4.0, "Attribution", https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
Reasons for limiting access	
Related output	

Dataset number	13
WP number	WP4
Creator	Peroni, Silvio (0000-0003-0530-4305)
Other contributor/s	Barzaghi, Sebastian; Massari, Arcangelo; Moretti, Arianna
Rights holder/s	Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna
Dataset title	CHANGES - SPOKE 4, Metadata of collections in University of Bologna's Museums
The data set is	new
Status	not yet available
Data types	Metadata
Data formats	RDF (following the CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model)
Dataset size	MB
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC 0, "No Rights Reserved", https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/public-domain/cc0/
Reasons for limiting access	
Related output	The datasets related to the acquisition and 3d modelling of the event "THE OTHER RENAISSANCE - Ulisse Aldrovandi and the wonders of the world" (14) and the museum Giovanni Capellini (15). Raw structured metadata describing all the objects of the exhibition and the acquisition process (21).

Dataset number	14
WP number	WP4
Creator	Peroni, Silvio (0000-0003-0530-4305); Pescarin, Sofia (0000-0002-9529-7083)

Other contributor/s	Ammirati, Luisa; Barzaghi, Sebastian; Bonifazi, Federica; Bordignon, Alice; Casadei, Veronica; Collina, Federica; Fabbri, Francesca; Fantini, Filippo; Ferdani, Daniele; Fiorini, Giulia; Forte, Anna; Giacomini, Federica; Girelli, Valentina; Lamorte, Marco; Manganelli del Fa, Rachele; Massari, Arcangelo; Moretti, Arianna; Pescarin, Sofia; Rega, Maria Felicia; Ronchi, Diego; Sorrentino, Stefano; Spedicati, Daniele; Sullini, Mattia; Tini, Maria Alessandra; Travaglini, Laura
Rights holder/s	Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna Italian National Research Council
Dataset title	CHANGES - SPOKE 4, Raster images, 3D Models and Data Specification of the exhibition "THE OTHER RENAISSANCE - Ulisse Aldrovandi and the wonders of the world"
The data set is	new
Status	in progress
Data types	1. Raster Images (acquired and processed photos, scans and panoramas) 2. 3D Models, containing geometry, material and texture information (exported from Photogrammetric/Scanner software) 3. Data Specification, for efficient transmission of 3D scenes and models targeting Web3D applications.
Data formats	1. *.jpg, *.raw - e.g. *.nef (Nikon), *.crw (Canon), *.arw (Sony), *.raf (Fuji), and *.scan (Artec) 2. *.obj, *.mtl, *.png, *.tiff, *.jpg, *.e57 3. *.glTF, *.glb - when exporting: UVs, Normals e Vertex color, with "Compression" if available
Dataset size	GB
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC0, "No Rights Reserved", https://creativecommons.org/public-domain/cc0/ when possible
Reasons for limiting access	It may be possible that, for some models, we need to specify a different license depending on the restrictions of the cultural heritage institutions, the person owning the original object or the Italian laws acting upon reproduction of Cultural Heritage objects.
Related output	The metadata describing all the objects of the exhibition (20).

Dataset number	15
WP number	WP4
Creator	Peroni, Silvio (0000-0003-0530-4305); Pescarin, Sofia (0000-0002-9529-7083)
Other contributor/s	Ammirati, Luisa; Bertelli, Valentina; Bordignon, Alice; Collina, Federica; Fabbri, Francesca; Fakharian, Nazanin; Pourhosseini Akbarie, Mahnoush; Rega, Maria Felicia; Sullini, Mattia; Wusiman, Kaosaier
Rights holder/s	Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna Italian National Research Council
Dataset title	CHANGES - SPOKE 4, Raster images, 3D Models and Data Specification of the museum Giovanni Capellini
The data set is	new
Status	not yet available

Data types	1. Raster Images (acquired and processed photos, scans and panoramas) 2. 3D Models, containing geometry, material and texture information (exported from Photogrammetric/Scanner software) 3. Data Specification, for efficient transmission of 3D scenes and models targeting Web3D applications.
Data formats	1. *.jpg, *.raw - e.g. *.nef (Nikon), *.crw (Canon), *.arw (Sony), *.raf (Fuji) and *.scan (Artec) 2. *.obj, *.mtl, *.png, *.tiff, *.jpg, *.e57 3. *.glTF, *.glb - when exporting: UVs, Normals e Vertex color, with "Compression" if available
Dataset size	GB
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC0 "No Rights Reserved", https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/public-domain/cc0/ , when possible
Reasons for limiting access	It may be possible that, for some models, we need to specify a different license depending on the restrictions of the cultural heritage institutions, the person owning the original object or the Italian laws acting upon reproduction of Cultural Heritage objects.
Related output	The metadata describing all the objects of the exhibition (20).

Dataset number	16
WP number	WP4
Creator	Marsili, Giulia (0000-0003-2732-0605)
Other contributor/s	Lamanna, Claudia (0000-0003-2464-3003)
Rights holder/s	University of Bologna; Parco archeologico di Morgantina e della Villa Romana del Casale di Piazza Armerina
Dataset title	CHANGES, SPOKE 4 - UNIBO, Villa of Piazza Armerina Villa digital reproduction
The data set is	New
Status	In progress
Data types	1. Raster Images (acquired and processed photos, panoramas) 2. Digital reproduction of archive materials (diaries, notes, pictures) 3. 3D Models, photogrammetric images of artifacts, findings and structures
Data formats	*.jpg, *.tiff, *.png, *.obj
Dataset size	Dataset size calculation in progress. Current estimation between 1 and 4 Terabyte
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	Under evaluation
Reasons for limiting access	Requirements of the rights holder (Parco Archeologico)
Related output	

Dataset number	17
WP number	WP4
Creator	Silvano Montaldo (0000-0003-0820-8730)

Oher contributor/s	Cristina Amitrano, Rossana Damiano, Stefano De Martino, Enrico Mensa
Rights holder/s	Fondazione Museo delle Antichità Egizie di Torino
Dataset title	CHANGES - SPOKE 4, WP4, Media items for museum storytelling experience, 1.0
The data set is	re-used; new
Status	in progress
Data types	3D and 2D models, audiovisual content, text (museum items and original content created for the storytelling experience)
Data formats	glTF, GLB, jpeg, tiff; txt, docx, html; json; mp3, mp4, mkv; other suitable formats will be taken into account at a later stage of the research; compressed formats will be preferred if available
Dataset size	500G
Repository	to be decided
License	CC BY 4.0, "Attribution", https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
Reasons for limiting access	
Related output	https://collezioni.museoegizio.it

Dataset number	18
WP number	WP4
Creator	Silvano Montaldo (0000-0003-0820-8730)
Oher contributor/s	Cristina Amitrano, Rossana Damiano, Stefano De Martino, Enrico Mensa
Rights holder/s	Università di Torino, Fondazione Museo delle Antichità Egizie di Torino
Dataset title	CHANGES - SPOKE 4, WP4, LLM benchmarking, 1.0
The data set is	re-used; new
Status	in progress
Data types	Text
Data formats	txt, csv, json
Dataset size	10G
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC BY 4.0, "Attribution", https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
Reasons for limiting access	
Related output	

Dataset number	19
WP number	WP4
Creator	Silvano Montaldo (0000-0003-0820-8730)
Other contributor/s	Cristina Amitrano, Rossana Damiano, Stefano De Martino, Enrico Mensa
Rights holder/s	Università di Torino, Fondazione Museo delle Antichità Egizie di Torino
Dataset title	CHANGES - SPOKE 4, WP4, Narrative patterns and vocabularies, 1.0
The data set is	re-used; new
Status	in progress
Data types	RDF and OWL documents, text
Data formats	JSON-LD, RDF (RDF/XML, Turtle), JSON
Dataset size	1G
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC BY 4.0, "Attribution", https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
Reasons for limiting access	
Related output	https://github.com/spice-h2020/SON

Dataset number	20
WP number	WP4
Creator	Silvano Montaldo (0000-0003-0820-8730)
Other contributor/s	Cristina Amitrano, Rossana Damiano, Stefano De Martino, Enrico Mensa
Rights holder/s	Università di Torino, Fondazione Museo delle Antichità Egizie di Torino
Dataset title	CHANGES - SPOKE 4, WP4, anonymized interaction logs, 1.0
The data set is	new
Status	not yet available
Data types	Text (anonymized logs of user behavior collected during the testing phase of the interactive storytelling experience)
Data formats	txt, csv, tsv
Dataset size	10G
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC BY-NC 4.0, "Attribution-NonCommercial", https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc/4.0/
Reasons for limiting access	Submitted to ethical considerations about the user-contributed origin of data
Related output	

Dataset number	21
WP number	WP1
Creator	Peroni, Silvio (0000-0003-0530-4305); Pescarin, Sofia (0000-0002-9529-7083)
Other contributor/s	Ammirati, Luisa; Barzaghi, Sebastian; Bertelli, Valentina; Bonifazi, Federica; Bordignon, Alice; Casadei, Veronica; Collina, Federica; Contessa, Michela; Daquino, Marilena; Fabbri, Francesca; Fakharian, Nazanin; Fantini, Filippo;

	Ferdani, Daniele; Fiorini, Giulia; Forte, Anna; Giacomini, Federica; Girelli, Valentina; Heibi, Ivan; Lamorte, Marco; Managlia, Annalisa; Manganelli del Fa, Rachele; Massari, Arcangelo; Moretti, Arianna; Pescarin, Sofia; Pourhosseini Akbarie, Mahnoush; Rega, Maria Felicia; Renda, Giulia; Ronchi, Diego; Sorrentino, Stefano; Spedicati, Daniele; Sullini, Mattia; Tini, Maria Alessandra; Tomasi, Francesca; Travaglini, Laura; Wusiman, Kaosaier
Rights holder/s	Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna Italian National Research Council
Dataset title	CHANGES - SPOKE 4, Raw metadata of collections in University of Bologna's Museums
The data set is	new
Status	not yet available
Data types	Tabular data
Data formats	csv, xlst
Dataset size	<10M
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC 0, "No Rights Reserved", https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/public-domain/cc0/
Reasons for limiting access	
Related output	The raw metadata, in tabular formats, describing all the objects in the collections involved (14, 15).

Dataset number	22
WP number	WP4
Creator	Stalteri, Cristina (0009-0009-6991-1383)
Other contributor/s	Montaldo, Silvano; Serati, Ilaria
Rights holder/s	University of Turin
Dataset title	CHANGES-SPOKE 4, WP4 SMA 04
The data set is	new
Status	in progress
Data types	Narrative contents for the digital storytelling of the Lombroso Museum's collection of posters with tattooed inmates
Data formats	.docx
Dataset size	40 KB
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC 0, "No Rights Reserved", https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/public-domain/cc0/
Reasons for limiting access	
Related output	The narrative contents include biographical information of the inmates that will be integrated in the installation on tattoos at the Lombroso Museum

Dataset number	23
WP number	WP4
Creator	Montaldo, Silvano (0000-0003-0820-8730)
Other contributor/s	Borra, Davide; Cavallo Perin, Roberto; Cilli, Cristina; Gagliarducci, Riccardo; Petrizzo, Alessio; Paruzzo, Francesca; Porru, Luca; Serati, Ilaria; Stalteri, Cristina
Rights holder/s	University of Turin No Real Interactive srl Brixel
Dataset title	CHANGES-SPOKE 4, WP4 SMA 05
The data set is	re-used; new
Status	not yet available
Data types	Texts are related to the manuscript on the tattoo collection of the Lombroso Museum and its digitization project
Data formats	.docx
Dataset size	1 Gb
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC BY 4.0, "Attribution", https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
Reasons for limiting access	
Related output	The dataset 'CHANGES-SPOKE 4, WP4 SMA 04' is related to this dataset

Dataset number	24
WP number	WP4
Creator	Stalteri, Cristina (0009-0009-6991-1383)
Other contributor/s	Borra, Davide; Decimo, Marc; Gagliarducci, Riccardo; Montaldo, Silvano; Pennacini, Cecilia; Porru, Luca; Petrizzo, Alessio.
Rights holder/s	University of Turin No Real Interactive srl Brixel
Dataset title	CHANGES-SPOKE 4, WP4 SMA 06
The data set is	new
Status	available
Data types	Speaker's presentation during the seminar: "I tatuaggi, le collezioni di Art brut e il cemì di cotone taino del Sistema Museale dell'Università degli Studi di Torino. Dalla loro storia alla sperimentazione di esperienze espositive tridimensionali, digital twin e web interattive".
Data formats	.pdf; .pptx.
Dataset size	1 Gb
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC BY 4.0, "Attribution", https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/

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Reasons for limiting access	
Related output	

Dataset number	25
WP number	WP
Creator	Genovese, Gianluca (0000-0002-1064-2061)
Other contributor/s	Roberto Montanari
Rights holder/s	Università degli Studi Suor Orsola Benincasa; Ente morale Istituto Suor Orsola Benincasa
Dataset title	Digital Cultural Objects from project MUSAD - SMA UNISOB (CHANGES – SPOKE 4)
The data set is	new
Status	in progress
Data types	Digital objects representing 1 album with 80 sheets featuring drawings by Tommaso de Vivo (first half of the 19th century), and 11 painted and gilded wooden sculptures (16th-17th centuries).
Data formats	.TIFF, .JPG; .OBJ, .GLTF/.GLB
Dataset size	10 GB ca.
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC BY-NC-ND 4.0, "Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivatives", https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-nd/4.0/
Reasons for limiting access	UNISOB policy.
Related output	Digitalization of artifacts used as test material in the virtual gallery prototype and digital archives developed in the SMA UNISOB – MUSAD project.

Dataset number	26
WP number	WP4
Creator	Genovese, Gianluca (0000-0002-1064-2061)
Other contributor/s	Montanari, Roberto
Rights holder/s	Università degli Studi Suor Orsola Benincasa
Dataset title	UX assessment data of SMA UNISOB - MUSAD project results
The data set is	new
Status	in progress
Data types	Data collected from anonymized UX test questionnaires and thematic analysis of interviews
Data formats	tabular, .xlsx
Dataset size	< 50 MB
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC BY 4.0, "Attribution", https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
Reasons for limiting access	The dataset is released under a CC BY 4.0 license to ensure that future research properly credits the original source. While the data is openly accessible, users are required to attribute the dataset in any derivative work or publication, in line with Open Science principles.

Related output	UX assessment data of SMA UNISOB - MUSAD project results
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Dataset number	27
WP number	WP4
Creator	Genovese, Gianluca (0000-0002-1064-2061)
Other contributor/s	Montanari, Roberto
Rights holder/s	Università degli Studi Suor Orsola Benincasa
Dataset title	UX assessment data of Reggio di Caserta - RC3DT project results
The data set is	new
Status	in progress
Data types	Data collected from anonymized UX test questionnaires and thematic analysis of interviews
Data formats	tabular, .xlsx
Dataset size	< 50 MB
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC BY 4.0, "Attribution", https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
Reasons for limiting access	The dataset is released under a CC BY 4.0 license to ensure that future research properly credits the original source. While the data is openly accessible, users are required to attribute the dataset in any derivative work or publication, in line with Open Science principles.
Related output	UX assessment data of SMA UNISOB - MUSAD project results

Dataset number	28
WP number	WP4
Creator	Zingari, Guido Nicolas (0000-0002-9670-1797)
Other contributor/s	Pennacini, Cecilia (0000-0003-4626-4290); Borra, Davide
Rights holder/s	University of Turin; No Real Interactive srl
Dataset title	CHANGES-SPOKE 4, WP4 SMA 07
The data set is	re-used; new
Status	in progress
Data types	Texts (contents for digital storytelling to be included in hotspots of Cemì 3D model: interview transcripts; research articles; excerpts from literary texts; virtual environment script; general documents)
Data formats	.pdf, .docx, .txt, .html
Dataset size	2 GB
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC BY 4.0, "Attribution", https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
Reasons for limiting access	
Related output	CHANGES-SPOKE 4, WP4 SMA 08

Dataset number	29
WP number	WP4
Creator	Zingari, Guido Nicolas (0000-0002-9670-1797)
Other contributor/s	Pennacini, Cecilia (0000-0003-4626-4290)
Rights holder/s	University of Turin
Dataset title	CHANGES-SPOKE 4, WP4 SMA 08
The data set is	re-used; new
Status	in progress
Data types	Texts (brochure; articles; catalogues; general documents)
Data formats	.pdf, .docx, .txt, .html
Dataset size	200 MB
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC BY 4.0, "Attribution", https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
Reasons for limiting access	
Related output	Article's manuscript on the methodological approach used in the Cemi digitization project, in particular, the application of VR and 3D modeling.

Dataset number	30
WP number	WP4
Creator	Zingari, Guido Nicolas (0000-0002-9670-1797)
Other contributor/s	Pennacini, Cecilia (0000-0003-4626-4290)
Rights holder/s	University of Turin
Dataset title	CHANGES-SPOKE 4, WP4 SMA 09
The data set is	new
Status	in progress
Data types	Images (video-interviews)
Data formats	.mp4, .mov, .mkv
Dataset size	150 GB
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC BY 4.0, "Attribution", https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
Reasons for limiting access	
Related output	CHANGES-SPOKE 4, WP4 SMA 04; CHANGES-SPOKE 4, WP4 SMA 07

Dataset number	31
WP number	WP4
Creator	Paruzzo, Francesca (0009-0003-9488-4555)
Other contributor/s	Cavallo Perin, Roberto (0000-0002-3217-6591)

Rights holder/s	University of Turin
Dataset title	CHANGES-SPOKE 4, WP4 SMA 10
The data set is	new
Status	in progress
Data types	Texts (brochure, articles, catalogues, general documents)
Data formats	.pdf, .docx, .txt, .html
Dataset size	500 MB
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC BY 4.0, "Attribution", https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
Reasons for limiting access	
Related output	Article's manuscript on topics related to Art Brut and tattoo collections of Lombroso Museum: data protection, copyright, protection of honour and reputation especially regarding heirs of prisoners and authors of art brut artworks.

Dataset number	32
WP number	WP4
Creator	Obbiso, Sara (0009-0004-2594-5251)
Other contributor/s	Benvenuti, Giuliana; Villani, Paola; Battilani, Patrizia; Bagnaresi, Davide; Stracuzzi, Riccardo; Iannucci, Alessandro; Giacomini, Federica; Mariniello, Nicola; Engineering spa; Sicilia, Ulderico; Risviel srl; Santopuoli, Nicola; Cattani, Maurizio; Mellara, Michele; Rossi, Alessandro; Mammot Film srl; D'Angelo, Francesca; Bonacini, Elisa; Corriero, Michele.
Rights holder/s	Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna Engineering Ingegneria Informatica SPA, Napoli Risviel srl Mammot Film srl UniBA - Università di Bari
Dataset title	CHANGES - SPOKE 4, WP4, Comprehensive Dataset of the Galtelli Literary Park
The data set is	re-used; new
Status	not yet available

Data types	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Photographs (e.g. digital reproduction of pictures and manuscripts, acquired and processed photos, scans and panoramas, digital reproductions, high resolution acquisitions) 2. Texts (e.g. excerpts of literary texts, brochures, flyers) 3. Spreadsheets (e.g. info about literary contents, tourist flows) 4. Audio (e.g. sound recordings, semi-structures interviews) 5. Video (e.g. footages, semi-structured interviews) 6. 3D models 7. PDF documents 8. Other (e.g. cross media books, tactile reproductions)
Data formats	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. .jpg; .jpeg; .png; .tiff 2. .txt; 3. .csv; .xlsx 4. .mp3; .wav 5. .mp4; .MOD; .mov; 6. .obj; .mtl; .e57; .ply; .gltf; .fbx; .glb; .x3d; .collada 7. .pdf 8. .stl; .3MF; .exr; .insp; .dng; .ARM; .ingp <p>other suitable formats will be taken into account at a later stage of the research</p>
Dataset size	150-200 GB
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC 0, "No Rights Reserved"; CC BY-SA 4.0, "Attribution-ShareAlike" when possible
Reasons for limiting access	More restrictive licenses may be necessary to protect the privacy of people participating in interviews or in the case of different needs of any surviving heirs of the author
Related output	Alignment with Aliano Literary Park dataset and contents

Dataset number	33
WP number	WP3
Creator	Renda, Giulia (0000-0003-2990-002)
Other contributor/s	Daquino, Marilena (0000-0002-1113-7550)
Rights holder/s	University of Bologna
Dataset title	CHANGES, WP3, MELODY v1.0.0
The data set is	re-used
Status	available

Data types	MELODY is primarily a data visualisation and storytelling platform built for use in Linked Open Data environments. It combines functionality across data querying, visualisation, and narrative creation. While it can be broadly categorised under Data-dominant software (A), its user-friendly features and focus on disseminating cultural heritage data align it with both consumer-oriented (A.con 3a Learning and Reference) and information display subcategories (A.inf 2 Standalone applications for displaying information, 3c User-generated content, 3l Web Authoring / Publishing Software).
Data formats	Python Files (.py), HTML Files (.html), JavaScript Files (.js), CSS and SCSS Files (.css, .scss), JSON Files (.json), Text Files (.txt)
Dataset size	Around 200MB. No extra storage needed.
Repository	Zenodo, polifonia-project/dashboard: v1.0.0 (https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037673)
License	ISC, "Internet Systems Consortium", https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ISC_license
Reasons for limiting access	No restricted access conditions.
Related output	

Dataset number	34
WP number	WP3
Creator	Renda, Giulia (0000-0003-2990-0021)
Other contributor/s	Daquino, Marilena (0000-0002-1113-7550)
Rights holder/s	University of Bologna
Dataset title	CHANGES, WP3, MELODY API
The data set is	new
Status	in progress
Data types	The API extending MELODY is a dynamic data retrieval and content delivery service designed to enhance interactions with cultural objects in digital environment. By processing user selections and configuration files, it bridges Linked Open Data querying with real-time HTML generation. Categorised under Data-dominant software (A), the API focuses on information display and transaction entry (A.inf).
Data formats	Python Files (.py), HTML Files (.html), JavaScript Files (.js), CSS Files (.css), JSON Files (.json), Text Files (.txt)
Dataset size	5KB
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	ISC, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ISC_license
Reasons for limiting access	No restrictions on access
Related output	

Dataset number	35
WP number	WP3
Creator	Moretti, Arianna (0000-0001-5486-7070)

Other contributor/s	
Rights holder/s	University of Bologna
Dataset title	CHANGES – Acquisition and objects
The data set is	new
Status	in progress
Data types	a dataset containing three ods tables and one csv table
Data formats	.ods, .csv
Dataset size	37.621 byte
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC 0, "No Rights Reserved", https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/public-domain/cc0/
Reasons for limiting access	
Related output	This dataset contains two samples, either re-arranged or extracted from a complete dataset that will be published by the end of the year 2024 (dataset 28).

Dataset number	36
WP number	WP3
Creator	Moretti, Arianna (0000-0001-5486-7070)
Other contributor/s	
Rights holder/s	Arianna Moretti
Dataset title	CHANGES Metadata Conversion Plugin (fork of: morph-kgc)
The data set is	new
Status	in progress
Data types	configuration (yaml, ini, toml), descriptive (md), input data (csv) and script (.py) files
Data formats	.py, .yaml, .ini, .toml, .md, .csv
Dataset size	45,9 MB
Repository	Zenodo/Software Heritage
License	Apache, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Apache_License
Reasons for limiting access	
Related output	The dataset is related to metadata in tabular format (dataset 20) and RDF format (dataset 28) for UNIBO collections.

Dataset number	37
WP number	WP1
Creator	Thun Hohenstein, Ursula (0000-0003-2835-3679)
Other contributor/s	Parisi, Chiara (0009-0005-6887-2467)

Rights holder/s	University of Ferrara
Dataset title	CHANGES_WP4_SMA_Museo_Leonardi_
The data set is	new
Status	in progress
Data types	Images 360, video, 3dmodels, audio, database, documents
Data formats	.jpg, .tiff, .png, .mp4, .obj, .pdf, .docx, .xlsx, .accdb
Dataset size	30 Terabyte
Repository	Zenodo
License	CC BY-NC-ND 4.0, "Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivatives", https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-nd/4.0/
Reasons for limiting access	We are waiting the permission by our institution
Related output	

Dataset number	38
WP number	WP4
Creator	Mariniello, Nicola (0000-0001-8309-2649)
Other contributor/s	Benvenuti, Giuliana; Villani, Paola; Battilani, Patrizia; Bagnaresi, Davide; Stracuzzi, Riccardo; Obbiso, Sara; Nicola, Mariniello Engineering spa; Monteleone Antonio; NAIS Solution, FORUM Team; Santopuoli, Nicola; Corriero, Michele; Bonacini, Elisa; Corriero, Michele.
Rights holder/s	Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna Engineering Ingegneria Informatica SPA, Napoli NAIS Solution srl Forum srl UniBA - Università di Bari
Dataset title	CHANGES - SPOKE 4, WP4, Comprehensive Dataset of the Aliano Literary Park
The data set is	re-used; new
Status	not yet available

Data types	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Photographs (e.g. digital reproduction of pictures and manuscripts, acquired and processed photos, scans and panoramas, digital reproductions, high resolution acquisitions); 2. Texts (e.g. excerpts of literary texts, brochures, flyers) 3. Spreadsheets (e.g. info about literary contents, tourist flows) 4. Audio (e.g. sound recordings, semi-structured interviews) 5. Video (e.g. footage, semi-structured interviews) 6. 3D models 7. PDF documents 8. Other (e.g. cross media books, tactile reproductions),
Data formats	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. .jpg; .jpeg; .png; .tiff 2. .txt; docx 3. .csv; .xlsx 4. .mp3; .wav 5. .mp4; .MOD; .mov; 6. .obj; .mtl; .e57; .ply; .gltf; .fbx; .glb; .x3d; .collada 7. .pdf 8. .stl; .3MF; .exr; .insp; .dng; .ARM; .ingp <p>other suitable formats will be taken into account at a later stage of the research</p>
Dataset size	150-200 GB
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC 0, "No Rights Reserved"; CC BY-SA 4.0, "Attribution-ShareAlike" when possible
Reasons for limiting access	More restrictive licenses may be necessary to protect the privacy of people participating in interviews or in the case of different needs of any surviving heirs of the author
Related output	Alignment with Galtelli Literary Park dataset and contents